

Synthesis of 1-Aza-6-thiacyclodeca-3,8-diyne

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The synthesis of 1-aza-6-thiacyclodeca-3,8-diyne derivatives (III) has been described.

INTEREST in the syntheses of heterocyclic alkadiynes arose as an offshoot from the possible aromaticity of Huckeloid annulenes. The diynes I and II were secured from such attempts^{1,2}. In this preliminary

note, we describe the synthesis of 1-aza-6-thiacyclodeca-3,8-diyne derivatives (III).

Our interest in the heterocycles (III) derives from the unusual interactions, we had earlier discovered, between sulfoxides and the triple bond and N-oxides and the acetylenic linkage³⁻⁵. One of our objectives is therefore to study the constraints placed upon such rearrangements owing to the Nitrogen and Sulfur atom being incorporated in such a closed system as III.

Additionally, a variety of other interesting features also lie in wait to be uncovered, *viz.* possibility of exciton interactions between the triple bonds; possibility of intramolecular cyclizations at the triple bonds catalyzed by transition metals leading to cyclobutadiene derivatives and interesting photochemical reactions emanating from the interaction of triple bonds in such close proximity.

The base-catalyzed condensation of 1,4-dichloro-2-butyne with aniline afforded the interesting "ethynlog" of the nitrogen mustard (IV) along with V and VI as byproducts in negligible amounts.

The relative proportions of the three products varied depending upon the nature of the solvent employed, ratio of reactants and temperature of the reaction. In the present communication we have focused our attention on optimizing the yields of IV (The chemistry of V and VI will be discussed in a later communication.)

Other ring substituted anilines showed similar product variations. The derivatives corresponding to IV varied in yields from 15% to 34%. These products were extremely sensitive to heat, (none of these could be distilled without decomposition) and were therefore purified by column chromatography using a special absorbent mixture, evolved after much trial and error (see experimental). Conversion of IV and analogs into III was accomplished in yields ranging from 5% to 40% depending on the aniline ring substituent. All of the derivatives of the system III were crystalline solids, with characteristic elemental analyses and spectral properties. Although the 1-aza-6-thiacyclodeca-3,8-diyne were stable solids at room temperature, prolonged exposure to light and air caused slow decomposition.

The metal catalyzed intramolecular transannular cyclizations of these alkadiynes will be reported in a subsequent communication.

Experimental

M.p.s were obtained on a Buchi-SMP-20 capillary melting point apparatus and were not corrected. NMR spectra were obtained in CDCl_3 solution using TMS as internal standard on a Varian A-60 spectrometer. Mass spectra were obtained on a DuPont-21-490B single focus high resolution instrument, at 70 eV. Ultraviolet spectra were measured in absolute ethanol solutions using a PYE-Unicam SP-1800 ultraviolet spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were provided by the Warner Lambert Research Institute.

General procedure for the synthesis of N,N-bis-(4'-chloro-2'-butynyl)anilines: A solution of 0.8 moles of potassium carbonate in 550 ml water was

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added to a solution of 0.4 moles of the aniline in 100 ml of acetonitrile. To this mixture was added a solution of 1.6 moles of 1,4-dichloro-2-butyne in 100 ml acetonitrile. The entire mixture was stirred vigorously under nitrogen at 45-50° for 2 days and for one day at 25-30°C. Progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC.

At the end of 72 hr., the organic and aqueous layers were separated and the aqueous layer extracted once with 100 ml of chloroform. The combined chloroform and organic layers were evaporated *in vacuo* to give 130g oily residue. From this residue 70g of unreacted

1,4-dichloro-2-butyne was distilled off at ca 30 : The product mixture was chromatographed over a column of two layers : A 1 : 1 mixture of acid washed alumina and silicagel (22 cm×10 cm) at the bottom and a 5 cm×10 cm bed of granular charcoal, alumina and CaCO₃ (in a ratio of 1 : 20 : 1) on top. This two phase column was developed with a mixture of 50% benzene and 50% hexane. Fractions of 200 ml were collected. Fractions 5 to 59 gave the pure N,N-bis(4'-chloro-2'-butynyl) aniline in a total yield of 30%.

Table 1 summarizes the PMR, UV, and elemental analyses of these derivatives.

TABLE 1. N, N-BIS-(4'-chloro-2'-BUTYNYL) ANILINES

Compound No.	Substituent R ₁	R ₂	% Yield	PMR (CDCl ₃) in S	U.V. max in EtOH, log _ε	Parent Peak in m.s.	G.R. Peaks	Calc.	Found.
1	H	H	33.6	4.00 (m, 8H), 6.7-7.4 (m, 5H)	206 230 245	4.73 4.37 4.27	265		
2	OMe	H	32.6	3.73 (s, 3H) 4.00 to 4.10 (m, 8H) 6.87-7.3 (m, 4H)	205 244 290	4.42 3.98 2.93	295	C 60.83 H 5.11 N 4.73	60.01 5.12 4.42
3	Br	H	21.8	4.00-4.10 (m, 8H) 6.7-7.30 (m, 4H)	208 255 295	4.36 4.13 sh	243 245	C 48.73 H 3.51 N 4.56	48.78 3.49 3.89
4	CH ₃	H	30.5	2.25 (s, 3H); 4.00-4.10 (m, 8H) 6.87-7.10 (m, 4H)	209 248 295	4.25 4.06 3.13	279	C 64.30 H 5.40 N 5.00	64.79 5.40 4.55
5	H	CH ₃	15.0	2.30 (s, 3H); 4.00-4.10 (m, 8H) 6.60-7.30 (m, 4H)	208 247 286	4.43 4.01 3.24	279		
6	Cl	Cl	15.0	4.10-4.15 (m, 8H) 6.55-7.35 (m, 3H)	212 258 286	4.50 4.31 3.36	335 330		

TABLE 2. 1-THIA-6-(N-ARYL) AZA CYCLODECA-3, 8-DIYNES

No.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p. (°C)	% Yield	Molecular Formula	Elemental analyses		PMR in CDCl ₃	λ _{max}	log ε	Parent Peak in MS
						Calculated	Found				
1	H	H	153°	40.00	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NS	C 73.97	74.18	3.37 (t, 4H)	206	4.15	227
						H 5.76	5.81	4.17 (t, 4H)	250	4.00	
						N 6.16	6.14	6.7-7.4 (m, 5H)	287	3.09	
						S 14.10	13.99				
2	OMe	H	152°	5.2	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NOS	C 70.01	69.72	3.80 (s, 3H)	206	4.33	257
						H 5.86	5.85	3.40 (t, 4H)	249	4.28	
						N 5.44	5.37	4.10 (t, 4H)	395	3.36	
						S 12.46	12.13	6.75-7.20 (m, 4H)			
3	Br	H	163°	35.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NSBr	C 54.91	C 54.96	3.47 (t, 4H)	206	4.33	304
						H 3.95	H 4.15	4.27 (t, 4H)	258	4.28	(306)
						N 4.57	N 4.56	6.90-7.65 (m, 4H)	295	3.25	
						S 10.47	S 10.44				
4	CH ₃	H	168°	36.9	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NS	C 74.65	74.63	2.30 (s, 3H)	206	4.36	241
						H 6.26	6.34	3.40 (t, 4H)	252	4.14	
						N 5.80	5.70	4.20 (t, 4H)	294	3.16	
						S 13.29	13.00	6.70-7.40 (m, 4H)			
5	H	CH ₃	154.5°	37.5	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NS	C 74.65	74.72	2.37 (s, 3H)	210	4.36	241
						H 6.26	6.51	3.40 (t, 4H)	252	4.14	
						N 5.80	5.78	4.02 (t, 4H)	287	3.24	
						S 13.29	13.02	6.60-7.40 (m, 4H)			
6	Cl	Cl	152°	40.9	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NS	C 56.77	56.44	3.40 (t, 4H)	213	4.41	295
						H 3.74	4.08	4.15 (t, 4H)	260	4.31	(297)
						N 4.73	4.76	6.70-7.40 (m, 3H)	304	3.30	
						S 10.82	10.78				

General procedure for the synthesis of 1-thia-6-(N-aryl) aza cyclodeca-3,8-diyne. To a solution of N,N-bis (4'-chloro-2'-butynyl) aniline (0.023 mole) in 500 ml of acetonitrile, a solution of sodium hydrosulfide (0.032 mole) and potassium carbonate (0.032 mole) in 200 ml of 75% aqueous methanol was added dropwise over an hour, at 25° under nitrogen and with vigorous stirring. The mixture was stirred for 3 hr more. The organic layer was separated and freed of solvents. The residue was extracted with 200 ml of chloroform; the extract was washed liberally with water, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and freed of solvent. The pale brown solid residue was purified by chromatography over the same kind of two phase column as was used in the purification of N,N-bis(4'-chloro-2'-butynyl) aniline. [20×4.5 cm of acid washed alumina and silica gel (1 : 1) as the bottom phase, topped by 5×4.5 cm of alumina and charcoal (5 : 8)]. The column was eluted with a 50-50 mixture of benzene and hexane. Fractions of 200 ml were collected. Evaporation of fractions 31 to 66 gave a 20% yield of the 1-thia-6-(N-aryl) aza cyclodeca-3,8-diyne.

Table 2 summarizes the characteristic data on these compounds.

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